

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT SITUATION OF THE MORTGAGE MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11570623>

Today, the need for modern housing for a large segment of the population is increasing day by day. A mortgage loan is one of the effective means of solving social, economic and legal problems in our country. Also, the creation of favorable conditions for meeting the population's demand for housing is inextricably linked with the development and expansion of the system of long-term mortgage housing loans.

In recent years, as a result of the expansion of the housing mortgage loan market in our country, the population's demand for housing is increasing. Accordingly, "mortgage centers" were established in order to provide practical assistance to citizens to conveniently and quickly implement mortgage loans.

In these centers, not only mortgage loans are allocated to citizens from the state budget, but also mortgage loans are allocated from the banks' own funds for the purchase of a house. This, in turn, is the main factor in the decrease of loan interest rates due to the emergence of an environment of competition between banks in the housing mortgage market.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 28, 2019 No. PF-5886 "On additional measures to improve mortgage loan mechanisms" on May 1, 2020 "Improving the housing conditions of the population and Resolution PQ-4701 on additional measures to further expand the mortgage credit market was approved. Also, Decree No. PF-51 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 13, 2023 "On measures to implement the program of providing housing to the population through mortgage loans based on market principles in 2023" was accepted.

In this decision, the acceleration of the processes of allocating mortgage loans based on market principles to provide housing to the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan was determined, as well as the evaluation of the factors influencing the further development of allocating mortgage loans for the purchase of housing to the population. the complexity and multifaceted nature of the problems is evident in practice.

Figure 1. Analysis of the amount of subsidy cost in the mortgage loan allocated to the population

In order to regulate the price of housing in the mortgage market, optimize resource costs in the state budget, and satisfy the population's demand for housing, we believe that it is appropriate to implement the following:

- To regulate the mortgage market in our republic, to control housing prices, to establish a "Housing Agency" that predicts the steady growth of the market development;
- Taking into account the increase in prices in the mortgage market, starting the construction of compact, small-sized apartments of 25-40 sq.m.;
- Shortening the term of the mortgage loan (by 5-7 years) in order to reduce excess interest payments when paying back the residential mortgage loan;
- Determining the amount of the initial contribution for the mortgage loan at 40%, in which the subsidy for the initial contribution allocated to the population will cover half of the total contribution from the state budget.

In conclusion, it should be said that banks show that special attention should be paid to the transformation of mortgage loans and the introduction of remote service systems on the basis of favorable conditions for the population.

- attracting financial resources in local and international capital markets, including funds from international financial institutions and foreign government financial organizations, and then directing them to refinancing mortgage loans;

- to help improve the mortgage credit system, implement modern methods and tools of mortgage market development, reduce risks and increase liquidity in the mortgage credit and mortgage securities market;

- participation in the development of the methodological and regulatory legal framework in the field of mortgage credit and refinancing, including involving foreign experts and specialists.

As a result of the fact that the above-mentioned conclusions and proposals are widely applied in practice, banks will ensure that this direction will be a priority today and in the future as a result of achieving priority and increasing their requirements for mortgage loans.

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